

Factsheet



The Dutch NBS site is located in the north of the Netherlands in a UNESCO World Heritage site with special natural values and an important role in maintaining the hydrological balance of the region. Unfortunately, intensive agriculture in the region, primarily potato production (also cereals, horticulture crops and fodder), has also caused the depletion of soil fertility and reduced agricultural productivity. Farmers are looking for innovative NBS solutions to restore this lost productivity, as well as enhance the resilience and efficiency of their farms.

NBS test site



An overview of the Dutch NBS test site alongside with an introduction to the alfalfa and grassclover pellets and solutions to reducing the virus spread infection in seed potatoes.

Jeroen Wolters presenting the Dutch NBS site and some experiments already conducted on the site.

Introduction to the Dutch NBS site



Cover crops in a potato based crop rotation



Are you looking for more information about different cover crops? See what can be used in a potato based crop rotation

Jeroen Wolters presenting cover crops in a potato based crop rotation

Cover crops in a potato based crop rotation



trans4num is a four-year project funded under the Zero Pollution call as an EU-China international cooperation action on nature-based solutions (NBS) for nutrient management in agriculture.

trans4num ambition is to broadly enhance the NBS implementation in Europe with an integrative and tested multi-level approach, in dialogue with academic partners, practice partners and societal stakeholders.

